

Optical Modules for Future Signal Processing Systems

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ABSTRACT

Optics is attractive for signal processing near the sensor end of systems because a large number of parallel channels is potentially possible, and the high carrier frequencies ($\approx 10^{14}$ Hz) allows very high channel bandwidths, but with little crosstalk. Since analog techniques are appropriate close to the sensor, these advantages can be obtained in a small volume. But, a number of disadvantages exist at present. Most well-known is the dynamic range limitation with analog. However, another equally important problem arises from the fact that analog optical modules must be part of a larger signal-processing system: it is difficult to pass information from an optical module operating near maximum throughput to the other parts of a signal processing system. The basis for this difficulty is often thought to be the high bandwidth and large number of channels of the optical module; but more quantitatively, optical modules i) do not yet have the capability to perform nonlinear operations on partially-processed data that would greatly reduce the module output rates and ii) require additional processing for equalization of channel response rather than for representation of useful information, and this processing is often left to the digital postprocessor. Recent work has been carried out at the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) to address the interface difficulty. One avenue is exploration of additional optical processing operations at the output of existing optical-processing modules, such as data compression (using moments, Walsh-Hadamard, and other orthogonal decompositions), adaptive data thresholding, and various multiplexed readout schemes. Another avenue is to explore reduction in precision requirements by employing in optical processors various adaptive learning techniques inherent in some parallel models of computation, such as neural net models. The third effort involves development of 2-D three-terminal, spatial light modulator devices that can provide the needed nonlinear transfer functions, the capability to cascade optical-processing operations, and throughputs greater than attainable with all-electronic approaches ($> 10^{10}$ pixels/s).

1. INTRODUCTION

Signal processing is simply the extraction of useful information from a noisy environment. But the techniques for doing this are not at all simple. Without going into textbook details, it will suffice to note here that the extraction process is multi-step, and generally involves both linear and nonlinear operations. It is generally desired to perform processing at high speed, and with capability for processing low signal-to-noise input signals. Optics promises high processing speed due to the large parallel channel capacity in two-dimensional (2-D) space and the high potential temporal bandwidth in each spatial channel. Additionally, optics has unique interconnection capabilities in 3-D space. A 2-D array of pixels may be remapped by propagation through passive optics; an especially well-known example is the Fourier transforming properties of a lens. Routing of light beams is the basis for optically performing a variety of linear operations needed in signal processing. Hence, optics has been used successfully to demonstrate Fourier

transformation (e.g., for 1-D and 2-D spectrum analysis), correlation, and matrix algebra (e.g., vector-matrix multiplication). The initial problem in such demonstrations is to impress information onto the light beam at a sustained rate commensurate with the speed capability of the optics. High-bandwidth, high-resolution light modulators are needed. This need has been met for 1-D signals using acousto-optic modulators [1] which can provide up to 2-GHz bandwidth and 2000 time-bandwidth. Specific 1-D and 2-D analog acousto-optic processors have demonstrated computation rates equivalent to 10 billion multiplications/sec [2]; the full throughput potential was not employed in these modules. (10^6 billion multiplications per second is theoretically possible with available components.) These processors, however, already encounter a problem at the output end, with data rates often so high as to preclude continuous communication with subsequent processing elements. This problem could become even worse when high-speed, high resolution 2-D spatial light modulators (SLM's) become available. Resolution of this output problem is dependent on application. In general, these high-speed optical modules are most effectively used for front-end operations (close to the sensor end of the system), and the output data-rate problem is resolvable for special situations where decisions for data passing are very straightforward and can be handled with high-speed electronics (e.g., simple threshold criteria).

Acousto-optic computation modules have therefore been constructed possessing unique capabilities for specific applications. Salient features of these existing modules can be identified:

- They perform only a single, fixed, function, although a single design, e.g., matrix processor, can be easily adapted to several applications. High speed demonstrations invariably involve only linear operations.
- Information flows through them only in the forward direction. Although feedback can be considered, there is no memory element as in digital computers; the only memory period available is the time required for data to pass through the module during processing.
- Because they are analog techniques, the processing capacity is high for a given processor size, weight, and power consumption.
- Because they are fixed-function processors employing analog techniques, dynamic range and precision are primarily hardware issues. Automatic gain control must be provided to obtain large dynamic range, and improved precision (beyond the 8-bit equivalent that is presently typical) can only be obtained with improved hardware.

The characteristics listed above indicate clearly that one does not have general purpose computation capability. However, it is not unrealistic to hope that a hybrid signal-processing system employing optical modules can provide greatly enhanced capability. Figure 1 shows how optical processors can naturally fit into a larger signal processing system; the optics handles large front-end computation loads, performing the initial stages of signal processing. Later stages must be performed with digital hardware capable of performing branching decisions, backtracking, etc., which are difficult, if not impossible, with these front-end modules. The system concept of Fig. 1 is one where a synergy is obtained between analog optics and digital

Fig. 1. Use of optical module near front end of larger signal processing system.

electronics, with analog electronics providing crucial transition functions at the sensor end and at the optical-digital interface. However, the concept of introducing optical modules for improving performance of a larger signal processing system is in consonance with some recent directions in advanced multiprocessor digital computer systems where specialized hardware modules are used to implement the primitive operations in a signal processing graph [3]. In fact, the problem statement for this area of digital computing is not specific to any technology: how can one make effective use of any high-speed computation hardware to speed the operation of a signal processing system. The answer, of course, lies in whether modules can be linked into appropriate architectures.

The degree to which a synergistic optical-digital system concept can succeed is dependent on the approaches to solving the input/output data rate problems for optical modules. This will generally mean a requirement that the modules perform more advanced functions, and in 2-D formats for maximum capability. The case will be made here that advanced modules can be obtained through the development of 2-D devices and techniques to provide i) capabilities for performing nonlinear operations on data, to reduce output bandwidths by allowing simple decisions on the data, ii) optical implementation of algorithms for data compression, iii) adaptive optical techniques that allow for reduced dynamic range requirements on processing, and iv) mechanisms for providing optical gain within the module, to allow expanded multistep processing. The following sections discuss work at the Naval Research Laboratory by the author and his co-workers on optical concepts for, and demonstrations of, a variety of operations that would make for more easy interfacing of optical processors. Attention is given device-performance needs in each case, with the final section a description of 2-D SLM developments that might meet some of these needs.

II. DATA COMPRESSION

It has been long recognized that raw imagery is generally not the most efficient representation of the information [4]. The same holds true for large data arrays in optical processors. There has been much work on image data compression techniques, and two that have been implemented optically will be described here - generalized moment representations [5], and orthonormal series expansion [4]. Optical implementation allows direct application to the 2-D data fields produced by optical processors, relieving the need for high-bandwidth, high dynamic range photodetectors needed in schemes where all subsequent processing is done electronically. Even if the subsequent processing is not particularly intensive, the transduction from optical to electrical representation is often difficult.

The generalized moment G_{mn} of a 2-D pattern $f(x,y)$ is defined as

$$G_{mn} = \iint f(x,y) g_{mn}(x,y) dx dy \quad (1)$$

where $g_{mn}(x,y)$ is the generating function (e.g., for geometric moments M_{10}, M_{01}, M_{20} , and M_{02} , the corresponding generating functions are x, y, x^2 , and y^2). For optical implementation, $g_{mn}(x,y)$ is modified as follows.

$$G_{mn} = \iint f(x,y) g_{mn}(x,y) \exp[-j\{(u-\mu u_0)x + (v-nv_0)y\}] dx dy \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} u=\mu u_0 \\ v=nv_0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Optical implementation of Eq. (2) is shown in Fig. 2. An intensity corresponding to the moment G_{mn} is produced at the location (u,v) in the frequency plane. A computer-generated hologram was constructed, encoding $g_{mn}(x,y)$ for nine geometric moments. The moment values are measured at the centers of the optical patterns located at positions $(\mu u_0, n v_0)$. Quantitative measurements were carried out with a binary rectangle with 2:1 aspect ratio along the x -axis. The rectangle was first centered with respect to the hologram by making its x and y moments equal, i.e., by equalizing the intensities for $+M_{10}$ and $-M_{10}$, and $+M_{01}$ and $-M_{01}$. The positive and negative xy moments provided similar information about the orientation of the rectangle; again, the positive and negative parts were equalized, thus making the xy moment zero as well. The square root of the ratio of the x^2 moment to the y^2 moment then corresponds to the aspect ratio of the input. Good agreement with theory was obtained (to about 1%). When the input is translated along the y axis or rotated the resultant intensity changes give information on the direction and magnitude of the shift and rotation [5]. The spacing of the intensity spots in the output plane was made large to minimize crosstalk. When both the phase and the intensity vary in the input image, crosstalk is of even greater concern; the output patterns obtained with a rectangle with a linear phase gradient is spatially smeared compared with the patterns for a uniphase object.

Fig. 2. Optical calculation of geometric moments.

Another data compression technique involves representing the original information as a series expansion using an orthonormal basis set (e.g., sinusoids, Walsh functions, Bessel functions, etc.) [4]. The coefficients of the individual terms in the series expansion therefore can be considered an equivalent representation of the information. An alternative description of this process is that the original information is a full 2-D matrix, $[G]$, and the desired coefficients are the elements of a diagonalized matrix, $[B]$, which is obtained by performing a similarity transform on $[G]$. The similarity transform is a triple matrix product operation which has been demonstrated optically. The triple-matrix-product operation may be written as

$$[B] = [U][G][V], \quad (3)$$

$$B_{ij} = \sum_k U_{ik} \left\{ \sum_l G_{kl} V_{lj} \right\} \\ = \sum_k \left\{ \sum_l U_{ik} G_{kl} \right\} V_{lj}$$

where the columns of $[V]$ are the orthonormal eigenfunctions of $[G]$, and $[U] = [V]^T$. One experimental implementation [6] of a triple-matrix processor is shown in Fig. 3. (Two additional implementations are discussed in Ref. 6.) The first half of the processor is essentially a matrix-vector processor multiplying the l th column of $[G]$ by matrix $[U]$, producing the l th column of the intermediate result ($[P] = [U][G]$). This column acts the input to an outer-product processor, to which the corresponding row (l th row) of $[V]$ is also input, resulting in an $N \times N$ outer-product matrix. N such outer-product matrices are summed in a 2-D time-integrating detector array to produce the final result $[B]$. This processor requires one 2-D SLM to input the matrix $[U]$, two 1-D SLM's to input a column of $[G]$ and the corresponding row of $[V]$, and a 2-D photodetector array to output $[B]$.

The processor of Fig. 3 has been used to perform a Walsh-Hadamard transformation on alphabetical characters. The results are shown in Fig. 4. The Walsh functions $W(0,0)$ through $W(7,0)$ were fed into two acousto-optic modulators at the positions

Fig. 3. Optical triple-matrix product processor.

Fig. 4. Optical Walsh-Hadamard transform.

for matrices $[G]$ and $[V]$, while the transparencies of the objects to be transformed were placed at the position indicated for matrix $[U]$. The outputs in Fig. 4 are the correct coefficients of the Walsh-Hadamard series expansion for the object, and are seen to require bipolar representation on a bias. Note that it was not necessary utilize a 2-D detector array for the output, as indicated in Fig. 3; the seven outputs were positioned along a single line for detection with a linear

photodetector array. For verification of correctness, the seven observed coefficients were then, however, introduced into the same processor, giving as output from a 2-D camera a sampled version of the original characters.

The moments and series expansion methods often do not work well in cluttered environments. However, when there is *a priori* knowledge of the characteristics of both the clutter signals and the signal of interest good performance can be obtained. While this is seldom the case in real-world imagery, it can often be the case in signal processing if appropriate preprocessing on the data array is performed. One of the most important preprocessing functions is adaptive thresholding, which will be discussed next.

III. ADAPTIVE THRESHOLDING

The desired output from an optical processor is often quite simple, e.g., a peak in optical intensity. However, reliable detection of such peaks in a large 2-D data array, at acceptable false-alarm rates, is difficult because of the speed and number of parallel channels (pixels), the presence of clutter, and variations in response across the data array. These difficulties are well known in 1-D signal processing, and a number of solutions are available. The most common approach is to use constant false alarm rate (CFAR) techniques which adaptively counteract variations in background or clutter levels. Essentially an estimate must be made of the background or sidelobe levels on either side of a candidate peak. The ratio of the peak power to the mean background power is then taken, normalizing signal levels. Thresholds are thus adaptively established with respect to normalized peaks. However, detection performance is always degraded, since a certain margin in signal-to-noise is required for a given probability of detection. This "CFAR loss" depends on the background statistics (assumed stationary) and the number of background samples used. The number of samples should not be so large as to average out significant background variations, but should not be so small as to produce poor statistics.

The CFAR implementation can be simplified by using a logarithmic representation for signals. The normalization is thus accomplished by subtraction, and there is an increased input dynamic range that can be processed. These advantages are particularly important when one considers an analog optical implementation, where division operations are generally not possible and dynamic range of the preprocessor is limited. This Log-CFAR algorithm [7] has been demonstrated electronically on a 1-D acousto-optical correlator, and can be implemented optically for operation on 2-D arrays.

The 1-D Log-CFAR implementation following an acousto-optical correlator is shown in Fig. 5. The background/sidelobe estimate is obtained by low-pass filtering the correlation function. Logarithmic amplification is performed on both the filtered and unfiltered functions. Normalization of the unfiltered function is obtained by feeding the two logarithmic signals into a comparator, effectively performing the division operation. The output of the comparator is then thresholded. Figure 6 shows the 1-D results obtained for a 13-bit Barker code correlation. In the upper right photograph are the filtered and unfiltered, log-amplified, correlation functions (lower traces); the uppermost trace, consisting of a spike corresponding to the correlation peak position, is the result of thresholding the output of the comparator. The two photographs on the left illustrate that the desired null result is obtained when correlation is destroyed by scale change, induced here by changing the data clocking. Further, the desired spike is obtained when the correlation function is on a steeply sloped background bias (lower right photo). Use of the spiked feature from the thresholded comparator output will reduce substantially the bandwidth needed to report the occurrence and location of a correlation peak, compared to, say, digitization of the entire correlation waveform. Further, use of Log amplification results in lower dynamic range requirements on other components.

Fig. 5. 1-D Log-CFAR implementation following an acousto-optic correlator.

Fig. 6. Results of 1-D Log-CFAR on 13-bit correlation results.

To extend the Log-CFAR algorithm to 2-D optical implementation requires first the logarithm of the intensity of an image. This may be achieved using a halftone-screen method[8]. The image must first be passed through the halftone screen consisting of identical cells with a shaped transmittance profile. The resultant product is then hardclip thresholded, as illustrated in Fig. 7 [after Ref. 8]; the output intensity is proportional to cell width which in turn is nonlinearly related to input intensity. The transmittance profile of the halftone cells is chosen here to give logarithmic transfer function. The optical thresholding requires a nonlinear device. Many available optical devices have nonlinear transfer functions, but the requirements are for a strong nonlinearity and an arbitrarily settable threshold. These requirements can be met with a spatial light modulator known as the MSLM (Microchannel Plate Spatial Light Modulator)[9] which employs electron-beam dynamics for addressing a modulating material. The modulating material is an electro-optic material such as LiNbO_3 . (A related device known as the PEMLM (Photoemitter Membrane Light Modulator)[13] employs a thin membrane as the modulating material. Both these devices will be discussed in detail in Section VI. The arbitrary threshold capability of the MSLM has been demonstrated on a 6-level grey scale[10]; those results, reproduced in Fig. 14. will be discussed in

Fig. 7. Logarithmic transform technique using halftone and thresholding [after ref. 8].

Section VI.) After Log transformation, the signal beam is beamsplit. The low-pass filter operation is performed on one leg via a simple blurring operation such as by Fourier-plane filtering. Comparator operation with the two beams requires a bipolar device; the MSLM device again satisfies the requirement. Charge may be either added or subtracted from the electro-optic modulating material, giving bipolar analog grey levels. Hence, the filtered and unfiltered image are applied sequentially to the MSLM. (The sequential operation is possible since the original image is held in the first MSLM which performed the thresholding for the log operation.) Finally, it should be noted that the number of grey levels available for the output Logarithmic representation is dependent on the resolution capability of the spatial light modulator, since pulse (or spot) width modulation is used in this remapping. In summary, the primary advantage is that the CFAR algorithm is performed in parallel on every pixel of the image.

IV. HIGH SPEED READOUT

In the previous Sections the problems were to rapidly reduce information in a large optical field to a relatively few peaks in intensity, and then to reliably identify the peaks among a background of spurious signals. Once these problems are solved, however, the new problem becomes one of quickly assessing the location of the peaks. Examination of the electrical output of a conventional photodetector array would commonly be done to accomplish this, but if the array is large and a number of peaks need to be identified e.g., as in the generalized moment technique discussed above, this cannot

be done quickly, even with parallel readout lines. For example, row-column matrix detection may be performed in some photodetectors[11]. However, this technique generally precludes detection of multiple signals along those particular rows and columns, or the determination of their amplitude. It has been suggested that rapid location of the threshold exceedances can be implemented optically[12]. The scheme proposed is illustrated in Fig. 8. An array of encoded light sources illuminate the rows of an optically-addressable 2-D SLM. The MSLM and PEMLM 2-D SLM's have detection sensitivities comparable to that of silicon photodetectors[9,13]. Each readout light source is identically encoded with a wideband modulation (e.g., PRN code), except for a 1-bit time slip between successive light sources. The columns of the readout field are then collapsed onto corresponding wideband photodetector elements. The photodetectors thus reproduce the wideband modulation signal for every threshold exceedance in the column. Location within the column is obtained by a matched filter operation on the photodetector outputs; different locations within a column produce the correlation peak in different time slots. 1-D acoustic pulse-compression filters were chosen for the matched filtering, since the available time-bandwidth of such devices appear well-matched to the column sizes expected in optical processors ($\approx 500 - 1000$), while being fairly compact. This scheme provides an intrinsic advantage in readout by remapping from two spatial dimensions to one each in space and time, thereby, allowing the more developed 1-D techniques to be used.

Fig. 8. Parallel optical readout scheme.

V. ADAPTIVE LEARNING/ FILTERING

Work described in the previous Sections is motivated by the desire to take full advantage of the large throughput of optics that derives largely from a unique capability for routing a large number of closely-spaced channels of light in three dimensional space. This interconnection capability can also be used to implement some parallel-processing approaches to pattern recognition and classification that can only be emulated (slowly) by serial digital machines. Pattern recognition and classification is often a very difficult problem because in real signal environments it is not possible to specify *a priori* all the relevant characteristics of the signals and clutter needed for classification. Feature-extraction work described in the previous sections only address the initial portion of the pattern recognition process. However, there are potentially powerful approaches to performing the entire process that rely on learning in a network of many simple processing elements (e.g., threshold elements) to automatically extract relevant features. Learning is manifested through adjustments in the weightings of the interconnections between elements. Although this approach is often known as "neural net" processing, the results often

resemble known signal-processing techniques, especially those from adaptive control theory[14]. The advantages to be gained must lie in rapid adaptivity, which provides proper responses after training cycles. Such adaptation also minimizes the disadvantage of low precision in analog components, allowing such components to perform effectively while generally providing size, weight and power consumption advantages over an all-digital electronic implementation. Since optics has the potential interconnection capability, and has been shown to be a workable analog technology, the primary issue is whether various types of adaptivity schemes can be implemented with optics to perform tasks ranging from initial filtering to final recognition and understanding.

Associative Modules

Association of patterns (or information arrays) can be considered to be the basic operation performed by a neural net. A particular response is obtained for a particular input after training with a set of data. Training cycles can be interspersed with recall operations if the input data has been corrupted or changed with time, but the meaning of the data (output) has not. An adaptive optical system has been demonstrated that learned a number of associated pairs of vectors and could recall the correct response when any one of the pairs was presented[15]. The ADALINE algorithm of Widrow and Hoff[14] was used in this demonstration for learning/training.

For associated patterns (or vectors) u and v , it is possible to construct an associative memory element using outer product multiplication of v and u^T , where T denotes the transpose operator. Using a matrix-algebra formulation, one can write associative recall of the vector v by the vector u as the vector matrix product

$$v = Mu \quad (4)$$

where M is the association matrix which is equal to vu^T for this case. With m associated vector pairs one can construct input/output matrices of size $n \times m$ denoted U and V respectively, where the columns consist of the individual vectors. Equation (4) then becomes a full matrix equation

$$V = MU \quad (5)$$

The matrix M in this case can be easily constructed if all m vectors u^i are mutually orthogonal. M is obtained as the sum of all the outer products of the associated vector pairs.

$$M = VU^T = \sum_{i=1}^m v^i(u^i)^T \quad (6)$$

It is easy to see that for orthonormal u^i vectors, Eq.(6) gives the proper result when operating on any of the vectors u^k :

$$Mu^k =$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m (v^i u^i)^T u^k = \sum_{i=1}^m v^i (u^i)^T \cdot u^k = v^k$$

However, the requirement for orthonormal vectors in Eq. (6) is generally very restrictive. One cannot solve Eq. (6) for M if U^{-1} does not exist (e.g., if U is not a square matrix). An adaptive M can provide an optimum solution such as the pseudoinverse solution[16] when the following differential equation for updating M is used

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = g(v^k - v)u^k \quad (7)$$

where v is the output at any given instant, v^k is the desired output for associated input u^k , and g an adjustable gain factor. Equation (7) is essentially the Widrow-Hoff algorithm. For implementation a difference-equation version of Eq. (7) was used.

$$M_{n+1} = M_n + gv^k u^k - gv u^k \quad (8)$$

where each associated vector pair is held constant for a time interval Δt , and $g = g' \Delta t$. In other words, the exact outer-product solution for the orthonormal case described by Eq. (6) is the starting point for iteratively obtaining the exact solution for the general case via Eq.

(8). The vector matrix products initially do not produce output vectors v equal to v^k ; a correction to the association matrix M is produced by subtracting the outer product of the input and v from the outer product of the input and v^k . This subtraction requires the use of a bipolar 2-D SLM such as the MSLM to be discussed in Sec. VI.

An optical implementation of the Widrow-Hoff ADALINE learning algorithm has been demonstrated [15]. Figure 9 is a top view of the implementation. The acousto-optic Bragg-cell modulators B_2 and B_3 combine with Fourier-transform lenses d and e and

Fig. 9. Optical implementation of the Widrow-Hoff ADALINE learning algorithm.

imaging lens f to produce an image of the outer product $v^k u^k$ on the detection side of the MSLM. The dashed-line optical path feeds the vector u^k forward to the modulator (readout) side of the MSLM, imaging in the vertical direction (via lenses g, i, j , and k) and spreading in the horizontal direction (via lens h). The feedforward u^k vector is produced by B_3 ; using the unmodulated light from B_2 . The horizontally spread u^k vector is multiplied by M as it reflects from the MSLM. This product is imaged (via lens l) along the dotted feedback path to a slit at Q . The cylindrical lens m performs a Fourier transform to form $v = Mu^k$ at the slit.

Experimental results from the full closed-loop Widrow-Hoff architecture are illustrated in Fig. 10. These results are for the system described by Eq. (8), with binary u^k , integer v^k , coherent illumination, and a 10- μm slit in the Fourier summation plane. The associated u^k and v^k vectors are displayed above photographs of the recalled v -vector intensities, as observed with a 1-D photodetector array. The observed results were obtained after thirty addition-subtraction cycles of the MSLM, corresponding to ten iterations over two vectors in Fig. 10(a) and fifteen iterations over two vectors in Fig. 10(b). Figure 10 shows the desired result: with training, a number of associated pairs may be stored as a memory matrix in a 2-D SLM such that activation by one element of any of the pairs correctly recalls the other element of the pair without being affected by the storage of the other, nonorthogonal, pairs.

In the ADALINE demonstration one of the more important aspects is that many characteristics of the components are never explicitly accounted for; e.g., non-uniformities in gain and optical transmission. These characteristics are automatically accounted for, and compensated, in the adaptation process, thereby allowing precision requirements on components to be much relaxed. However, output dynamic range was limited to only a few grey levels by low optical energy densities at the output plane. Although gain is provided by the MSLM in the detection and storage of the memory matrix M , no

Fig. 10. Experimental results for associative recall using Widrow-Hoff implementation.

gain was provided in the feedback and feedforward paths. Also the use of acousto-optic cells here was very wasteful of light; the laser source was shuttered with an external modulator at a speed adequate to freeze-frame the vector information flowing through the Bragg cells. Use of an additional MSLM as a light beam amplifier, and development of high efficiency non-travelling-wave 1-D modulators will provide more output dynamic range. On the other hand, much of the promise of associative recall is that even with few grey levels large numbers of vectors can still be processed. For example, with p grey levels and N elements in a vector, p^N different vectors may be generated.

The development of associative architectures employing a multiplicity of associative modules for solving problems such as image understanding, speech understanding and synthesis, robotic manipulation and locomotion, and expert-system problem solving is presently a very active field. Organizational principles for designing these architectures need to be further developed. Issues include the control of the modules to implement desirable features such as incremental learning, gated learning, gradient-driven learning, avoidance of saturation, and controlled forgetting. Discussion of these is, however, beyond the scope of this paper. [See list of references in Ref. 15.] In the above, only a particular subset of the possible optical tools has been applied to demonstrate some of the desired features in an associative module. It can be expected that the optical techniques will be refined concurrently with the algorithmic advances.

Filtering

Reduced dynamic range requirements are a focus of the above discussions. However, it is obvious that dynamic range requirements are relaxed if desired signals can be initially separated from undesired signals. In fact, adaptive techniques to perform such preprocessing operations have been developed, often with formulations resembling those for neural nets [14]. For example, an adaptive system can be made to remove or desensitize response to strong cw interference signals, allowing low-level broadband signals to be analyzed. Optical implementations of adaptive transversal

filter techniques for performing this function have been investigated by a number of researchers[17,18]. The total signal is passed through a tapped delay line and a correlation is performed with a set of weights that correspond to the strength of the interference signal to be removed. The correlation coefficients that result are then used to obtain, via a convolution, an estimate of the interfering waveform. The estimated waveform is then subtracted from the total signal, and the residual is used both as the new input into the tapped delay line and as the weights for another stage of correlation with the tapped delay line signals. With convergence, the residual represents the interference-free broadband signal. This iterative procedure has strong similarities to the ADALINE formulation discussed above. A compact, real-time, implementation of this filtering technique is desirable. Optical techniques have the required speed and compactness, but the necessity to cascade two optical operations (the tapped delay line correlation and the convolution with the resultant correlation coefficients) makes it difficult to achieve a reasonable dynamic range in the absence of signal amplification within the cascade, just as in the ADALINE demonstration. Section VI will deal with development of devices that can provide the necessary gain for these applications.

VI. 2-D SPATIAL LIGHT MODULATOR (SLM) DEVELOPMENT

The development of 1-D acousto-optic devices has led to the demonstration of high-speed, compact, modules for performing linear signal-processing operations. While it is clearly desirable to obtain similar speed capabilities in 2-D for electrical to optical or optical to optical transduction, it may be much more important to develop capabilities for performing operations such as those discussed in the previous Sections. Even at lower frame rates, such capabilities would complement the speed of acousto-optic processors.

The Microchannel Spatial Light Modulator (MSLM) and the Photo-emitter Membrane Light Modulator (PEMLM) are two 2-D Spatial Light Modulators that have been mentioned in Sections III-V several times as crucial components for demonstrating desired operations. These particular SLM's have been chosen for a number of demonstrations because they possess a number of characteristics critical to practical optical signal processors, these include: internal gain, bipolar operation, very high optical sensitivity, and arbitrary threshold capability. Thresholding permits nonlinear transfer functions to be generated, such as logarithmic (see Sec. III), which is important for reducing the amount and bandwidth of data in optical processors. Internal gain and high optical sensitivity allow optical operations to be cascaded, e.g., for linear operations to be followed by nonlinear ones, and for iterative optical feedback techniques needed in adaptive algorithms (Sec. V). Bipolar operation is also crucial for implementation of adaptive and learning algorithms, system correction, and comparison operations.

Device Description and Operation

The desirable characteristics of the MSLM and PEMLM arise from electron-beam dynamics in a structure incorporating a microchannel-plate (MCP) electron multiplier. The basic structure of an optically-addressed SLM incorporating an MCP is shown in Fig. 11. The input writing image impinges on basically an image-intensifier structure, consisting of a photocathode-MCP arrangement, but rather than a phosphor screen, the arrangement is followed by an optical modulating material -- a thin electro-optic plate (e.g., LiNbO_3) for the MSLM, and a thin (≈ 50 nm) membrane of material such as nitrocellulose for the PEMLM. Deposition of charge onto the modulating material in both modulators results in phase modulation of the readout beam, with subsequent amplitude modulation with polarizing or interferometric readout optics. Charge of either polarity may be deposited. Charges are removed by bias-voltage polarity reversal and using secondary emission characteristics[19,20]. An electrically addressed variant of Fig. 11 replaces the input optical beam with an electrical addressing mechanism such as a scanned electron beam. An extensive amount of

Fig. 11. Structure of an optically-addressed SLM employing a microchannel plate

of development has been done; the MSLM is available in both optically and electrically addressed versions[22,23], and a number of prototypes are being developed for both the MSLM and the PEMLM[24].

The availability of internal gain (from the MCP) allows for virtually quantum-limited sensitivity in the optically-addressed devices. Full contrast responses can be obtained with only a few photons/pixel, although in practice it is usually desirable to operate with reduced gain or lower resolution, thereby integrating more primary photons for an increased quantum-limited signal-to-noise ratio. For the specific case of the PEMLM[20] with a $6 \mu\text{m}$ radius membrane, a photocathode quantum efficiency of 10% at 633 nm, and an MCP gain of 8400, full contrast modulation can be obtained with 50 photons/pixel, corresponding to a calculated write energy of only 140 pJ/cm^2 or 0.016 fJ/pixel . This is about 50X less than the lowest reported energy required to switch a single bistable optical element (of the Fabry-Perot-cavity type)[25], although the switching speed there is about 1 ns, while at best the speed here would be several hundred nanoseconds. On the other hand, the MSLM and PEMLM are three-port, image-multiplying devices with isolation between input and output; while three-port bistable devices exist (e.g., Self Electro-optic Effect Devices, SEED's[26]), the required switching energies are orders-of-magnitude higher.

Many of the interesting capabilities of the MSLM and the PEMLM arise from the electron dynamics associated with the basic structure. These dynamics govern the deposition and removal of charge from the modulating material, and result in the ability to add and subtract data arrays, to synchronously detect a temporally modulated intensity object (i.e., perform as a pixel array of lock-in detectors), and to perform a fully programmable threshold operation. Since the programmable threshold is such a unique and crucial aspect of these devices, a short review of the mechanisms involved will now be given.

One way of obtaining threshold operation on an optical field with these devices is to first uniformly pre-charge an insulating target (the modulating material) with electrons, and then using the electrons generated by the optical information in an optically-addressed device to "erase" (via excess secondary-electron emission) the uniform charge. Erasure of the charged target occurs only where the input intensity is above a critical level, determined by the rate-of-change of an externally-controlled bias voltage (V_b) applied to the target[20,27]. This behavior can be qualitatively understood by referring to Figs. 12 and 13, which model the device as a parallel-plate capacitor system, where i_g is the current flowing to say the crystal in the MSLM (XTAL in Fig. 12), and V_0 is the voltage between the crystal and a metal grid that follows the electron source, V_b is the voltage applied to the transparent electrode on the crystal, V_C is the applied grid voltage, and V_X is the voltage drop across the crystal itself. Depending on the value of V_0 , the polarity of i_g may be either positive (deposition of electrons) or negative (secondary-emission removal of electrons). Much of the electron

physics is summarized in curves showing the basic dependence of i_g on V_g , shown in Fig. 13 for two intensities ($A > B$); these solid curves are simply scaled versions of each other. Normally, a stable equilibrium occurs at $V_g = V_{g0}$, where $i_g = 0$. An increase of V_g causes electron buildup on the crystal ($i_g > 0$), driving V_g more negative, back towards V_{g0} . A decrease of V_g allows more secondary emission electrons to escape from the crystal ($i_g < 0$), driving V_g more positive. Examination of Fig. 13 reveals that a change in the external bias voltage V_b produces two contributions to changes in the current i_g . The first is a change in the amount of photocurrent from the MCP. The second is a capacitive displacement current term related to the voltage-time derivative.

$$i_g = C_x(\dot{V}_b - \dot{V}_g) \quad (9)$$

In the absence of any electrons from the MCP, this capacitive displacement current will change V_g ($\dot{V}_g = i_g/C_g$). However, in the presence of the MCP photocurrent, a new stable equilibrium point can be maintained, despite the changes in V_b ; i.e., $\dot{V}_g = 0$ and Eq. (9) becomes

$$i_g \approx C_x \dot{V}_b \quad (10)$$

The new equilibrium point occurs at $V_g = V_{g1}$ in Fig. 13, where the i_g vs. V_g curve for intensity A intersects the load line described by Eq. (10), the horizontal dashed line for $V_b < 0$. At this equilibrium the MCP-driven current transports charge between the crystal and grid at the same rate displacement-current charge is being applied from V_b , preventing any net charging of C_g and resulting in the total

Fig. 12. Parallel plate model for the MSLM

Fig. 13. i_g vs. V_g for the MSLM.

capacitive charge from V_b being applied to the crystal, V_x (i.e., $\Delta V_g = 0$ and $\Delta V_x = \Delta V_b$). The stability of this equilibrium point can be further understood by considering two cases. If $V_g > V_{g1}$, then the MCP-driven current ($|i_g|$ on the i_g vs. V_g curve of Fig. 13.) is smaller than $|C_x \dot{V}_b|$, and there is excess, uncompensated capacitive displacement current driving V_g more negative (remembering that $\dot{V}_b < 0$). If $V_g < V_{g1}$, then $|i_g| > |C_x \dot{V}_b|$ and the excess i_g charges C_g more positive.

There is no new equilibrium point if the optical intensity is too low to make the i_g vs. V_g curve intersect the load line (e.g., intensity B in Fig. 13). The full capacitive displacement current from V_b is then coupled into V_g , i.e., $\Delta V_g = \Delta V_b$ and $\Delta V_x = 0$ (Note: $C_x \gg C_g$). There are thus two operating regimes, separated by a distinct intensity threshold which occurs at the intensity where the i_g vs. V_g curve shifts to just cross the load line, Eq. (10). Write-image regions with intensities I_w below the threshold I_t produce no change in output modulation (since $\Delta V_x = 0$), and the intensities exceeding the threshold produce a full change in modulation (with $\Delta V_x = \Delta V_b$). This threshold intensity is given by

$$I_t = \left[\frac{h\nu}{nqGA} \right] \frac{C_x \dot{V}_b}{F(V_{gp})} \quad (11)$$

where $F(V_{gp})$ is the most negative value of i_g on a normalized i_g vs. V_g curve in Fig. 13, and the bracketed term converts current into optical intensity. A more rigorous analysis[27] shows that for $I_w < I_t$, the crystal or membrane charge (or voltage change) is proportional to $\ln(1 - I_w/I_t)$, which often produces a very distinct threshold for typical device parameters. The two output modulation levels can be arbitrarily set by the choice of starting and ending voltages for the decreasing ramp in V_b . Ramping rates for V_b as high as 1500V in 1 millisecond are easily obtained. Therefore, one has an externally programmable thresholding operation, with independently settable input threshold and output modulation levels.

Figure 14 shows experimental results using the MSLM for hard-clip thresholding. The 6-level grey scale image in Fig. 14 was thresholded at five different adjustable threshold levels in Figs. 14b-14f. The two output levels were set for an inverted contrast response. The same device was then used to perform edge enhancement on an analog image by setting the above- and below-threshold output levels at the same grey level, but separated in phase by 2π [28].

Fig. 14. Hardclip threshold results using MSLM.

Most demonstrations of device capabilities have been performed with the MSLM. Due to its relatively more mature status, facilities exist for fabrication of reliable MSLM devices for research purposes[21, 29]. The MSLM, however, has a fundamental drawback. There exists a tradeoff between speed and resolution related to the finite thickness of the lithium niobate plate onto which charge is deposited[9]. The largest value obtained to date for the product of frame time and resolution (or space-bandwidth, SBW) has been about 10^7 /sec, with frame rates as high as 100/sec[9] at low resolution, and SBW as high as 5×10^5 spots[21] at slow frame rates (3 frames/sec). The PEMLM has therefore been investigated for increased Speed-SBW product over that offered by the MSLM. Theoretical calculations[20] show that the Speed-SBW product for the PEMLM can be as high as 10^{11} /sec. Since the resolution in the

PEMLM is determined by the pore spacing of the MCP, space-bandwidth of $>10^8$ (i.e., resolution of >50 line pairs/mm) is possible, based on available sizes for microchannel plates with <10 μm pore spacing. The frame time can be <1 ms, based on maximum currents available in state-of-the-art MCP's. A speed-resolution tradeoff also exists for the PEMLM, although at a much higher level. By using reduced pore size in to obtain higher resolution, there will be fewer electrons per pore at the charge density for say half-wave membrane deflection; this results in a higher level of shot noise relative to signal. Hence to maintain the same signal-to-noise at individual pixels, a larger exposure is required. A similar consideration occurs if the MCP size is increased for the same pore size and constant input optical power.

The PEMLM also exhibits most of the desirable features found in the MSLM:

- Storage times of hours; this depends on the resistivity of the reflective coating on the membrane (needed for optical readout; see Fig. 11),
- Quantum-limited sensitivity, as noted previously
- Phase dynamic range of $>2\pi$, as indicated by contrast reversal of output with increasing optical exposure,
- Capability for nonlinear image-processing operations in real-time and on stored images,
- Capability for synchronous detection.

Good image quality has also been obtained with the PEMLM, as shown in Fig. 15, even with very non-flat MCP's (25-50 waves), by properly designing the Schlieren readout filter. As with the MSLM, either parallel or serial input is obtainable. The current status is that experiments have been performed which verify that all the above performance characteristics should be obtainable. Images have been written on MCP's with 15 lp/mm resolution, and 10 msec writing and erasure times have been demonstrated using a strong UV source to produce photoemission from the front electrode of the MCP [24].

Fig. 15. Imagery obtained with the PEMLM.

Application

The variety of demonstrated capabilities for the MSLM and the PEMLM lead can lead to the interesting viewpoint that these devices can be generally considered preprocessing 2-D photodetector arrays that address many of the problems of at the input and output interfaces of optical processors. The prerequisite sensitivity exists, and the option for fully parallel readout/search was discussed in Section IV. However, several further examples can be cited.

i) Synchronous detection, discussed earlier, can be used to separate desired from undesired signals at the input. The left picture in Fig. 16 is an image consisting of two superimposed objects, an airplane and a C-clamp. Recognition of either requires that the other be filter out entirely. Since the intensities of the two objects were

made to oscillate at different frequencies, by modulating the sensitivity of the MSLM device at one of these frequencies, one can separate out the image of either the airplane (center) or the C-clamp (right photo). Application in specific areas such as robotic machine vision is evident.

Fig. 16. Synchronous detection with the MSLM.

iii) The MSLM is capable of performing zooming, shifting, and rotation on an input scene via control of electron-imaging optics [22]. This capability could be useful in target recognition problems employing search routines. For example, in the classic Fourier-transform correlator, sensitivity to scale and aspect is handled by employing a multiplicity of Fourier-plane filters; these must either be multiplexed or serially inserted into the system. Hence, this MSLM capability could alleviate the difficulties of multiplexing many filters onto a single spatial light modulator or the requirement for high-speed accessing circuitry between a memory and the filter-plane SLM.

Further Developments and Issues

While enormous performance potential is evident for these MCP-based SLM's, there are still a number of shortfalls. The primary performance parameter sought is larger Speed-SBW product. Also, while not of a fundamental nature, practical issues such as manufacturability, ease of usage, and reliability are as crucial as improving intrinsic improved performance, and will require novel approaches. For example, these devices rely on standard photocathodes that are limited to wavelengths shorter than 700 nm and have limited photocurrent output. Also, fabrication and materials must be compatible with the fabrication and characteristics of photocathodes which are notoriously susceptible to poisoning and must be baked and kept under ultrahigh vacuum; this is a particular worry with the nitrocellulose membrane in the PEMLM. Work is continuing on investigation of PEMLM operation with other membrane materials that can withstand high-temperature, high vacuum bakeout, such as Al_2O_3 and parylene, and using physical isolation techniques between the membrane and photocathode regions (e.g., use of electron-permeable membranes).

Many optical processors operate at laser diode wavelengths near 830 nm, so photocathodes sensitive at this wavelength need to be incorporated (e.g., Si-type or GaAs photocathodes). However, recent demonstration of arrays of tiny, sharply-pointed silicon or metal field emitters [30], raises the possibility of VLSI fabrication of "synthetic" photocathodes with very high current-carrying capability and tailored spectral response. The concept for optically-activated arrays of field emitters is illustrated in Fig. 17 for bottom and top illumination; photocharge results in field emission from the tips. Such structures could also obviate many materials compatibility issues and increase device speed. Speed can also be significantly enhanced by employing recently developed MCP technology having very high strip current. The write/erase times for the devices are ultimately limited by the currents available from the MCP. Strip currents of 100 mA/cm² now appear feasible, or 1000 times present levels, implying similar frame-time speedup.

At the output, an increase in dynamic range would be desirable. Generally, this requires higher quality on the components. For example, the Schlieren readout of the PEMLM would be improved with an optically-flat MCP. However, increased dynamic range need not be an overriding concern; if sufficient processing has been performed on the data, as discussed in in the previous Sections, a low dynamic range output can suffice.

Fig. 17. Optically-activated array of field emitters.

VII. SUMMARY

The common theme in the topics discussed is the need to pass information effectively from high-speed optical processors to subsequent stages in a signal-processing system. Difficulties arise primarily because of mismatch in processing rates, but also due to dynamic range limits. Some of the additional operations that need to be performed by optics to alleviate the data-rate mismatch problem have been identified. They include data re-representation such as by the coefficients of a moments expansion or another orthonormal expansion, and nonlinear operations, especially adaptive thresholding. Adaptivity can be used to reduce dynamic range requirements and provide alternative, perhaps more effective methods for performing image processing and recognition operations with low-precision components. However, the key to the required optical implementations is the development of certain device characteristics for light modulation and "smart" photodetection: programmable and adaptive thresholding, sensitivity, gain, and bipolar operation. The MCP-based SLM's have been chosen for development because they provide many of these required qualities.

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